

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Impact of celebrity endorsement on purchase decision-making of students in Centro Escolar University-Manila towards beauty products

Joshua D. Gabucayan ^{1,*}, Chrisse Andrei O. Alayu ¹, Sheena Mari A. Alden ¹, Hazel Joy D. Amponin ¹, Shelley Mae C. Apostol ¹, Andrea Marvy P. Banga-an ¹, Roann Alyza B. Santos ¹, Angeline C. Serna ¹, Mary Joy B. Tabor ¹ and Chastine Therese S. Villaester ^{1, 2}, Cecilia D. Santiago ^{1, 2} and Mylene S. Andal ¹

¹ Bachelor of Science, School of Pharmacy, Centro Escolar University-Manila, 9 Mendiola St, San Miguel, Manila 1008, Metro Manila, Philippines.

² Graduate School, Centro Escolar University-Manila, 9 Mendiola St, San Miguel, Manila 1008, Metro Manila, Philippines.

GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2022, 20(01), 206–211

Publication history: Received on 01 June 2022; revised on 11 July 2022; accepted on 14 July 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2022.20.1.0273>

Abstract

This study aims to determine the impact of celebrity endorsement on the purchase decision-making of the consumers represented by the students in Centro Escolar University Manila towards beauty products. This descriptive correlational quantitative study will use Spearman Rank Correlation to quantify the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The respondents will be selected using the proportionate sampling technique, and the sample size will be computed using Slovin's formula. There will be four sections of the questionnaire containing: (1) socio-demographic profile of the respondents, (2) types of celebrity endorsers, (3) impact of celebrity endorsements on purchase decision making based on their different quality attributes, (4) relationship of identified qualities of celebrity endorsers to respondents purchase decision making. The collection of data was conducted through Google forms to examine the objectives of the study and was analyzed using the statistical tool Spearman Rank Correlation to further analyze the results of the study at 0.05 alpha levels. The research concluded that there was a significant relationship between consumers' purchase decision-making and attractiveness ($r= 0.263$), expertise ($r=0.291$), and credibility ($r=0.122$) traits of endorsers. The overall results show that attractiveness has a weak positive correlation with the purchase decision-making of the respondents towards beauty products while traits of expertise and credibility have a negligible positive correlation.

Keywords: Celebrity Endorsement; Beauty Products; Purchase Decision Making; Celebrity Endorser

1. Introduction

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) [1] defines beauty products as items intended to enhance an individual's physical appearance. According to Diller [2] it helps people feel better, look better, boost self-esteem and even express their unique style of social expression. In the market, the beauty industry is a lucrative field for business owners; it is valued at \$486 billion in 2020 and is expected to reach \$716 billion in 2025 [3]. To gain an advantage over their competitors in the industry, companies in the Philippines would make use of individuals to advertise their products to the public by making use of artists, singers, and young models that seem credible enough to raise awareness of the product to the community, however because of the wide range of individuals having the capability of endorsing beauty products, choosing which endorser is more likely to impact the purchasing decision of the consumers is important.

* Corresponding author: Joshua Dela Victoria Gabucayan

Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy, School of Pharmacy, Centro Escolar University, Manila 9 Mendiola Street, San Miguel, Manila City, Philippines.

Past research implemented various theories to address such concerns, the most notable ones include Source Credibility Theory and Source Attractiveness Theory indicating that people are more likely to be persuaded of an endorser's level of credibility, trustworthiness, expertise, and attractiveness [4]. Therefore, this study aims to determine the impact of celebrity endorsers on the purchase decision-making of the consumers of beauty products by making use of respondents from Centro Escolar University Manila for SY. 2021-2022.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study Design

This study used a descriptive quantitative correlational research design to measure the study variables and assess the corresponding relationship between them, namely: (1) the impact of identified quality attributes of celebrity endorsers and (2) purchase decision-making of students in Centro Escolar University-Manila towards beauty products.

2.2. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were students from all undergraduate schools of Centro Escolar University-Manila enrolled for the academic year 2021-2022.

2.3. Number of Respondents and Sampling Techniques

The researchers obtained 384 respondents by calculating the sample using Slovin's formula. This study utilized a proportionate sampling technique for each undergraduate school.

2.4. Research Instrument

The online survey questionnaire consisted of four sections based on the research objective: (1) socio-demographic profile of the respondents, (2) types of celebrity endorsers, (3) impact of celebrity endorsements on purchase decision-making based on their different quality attributes, and (4) relationship of identified qualities of celebrity endorsers to respondents purchase decision making.

2.5. Collection of Data

The researchers made use of Google form in collecting the necessary information from the respondents using an online questionnaire as a material. The data collected were filed in a secured place provided that their respective emails were saved and validated the reliability of the survey.

2.6. Statistical Treatment of Data

The study variables were analyzed with the assistance of a registered statistician and the collected data was tallied, tabulated, and analyzed quantitatively using the following statistical treatments: (1) percentage, (2) weighted mean, (3) standard deviation, and (4) Spearman rank correlation.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1 Distribution of Respondents based on Sex

From the 384 respondents, the majority are female (85.16%). Females are more likely to participate in the survey as they are interested in the topic and more willing to participate in the research study [5].

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents' Choice of Celebrity Endorsers

Celebrity Endorser	<i>f</i>	%
Vloggers	203	70.20
Actors/Actress	57	19.70
Athletes	13	4.50
Bloggers	8	2.80
Singers	8	2.80

Most of the respondents believe that their purchase decision-making is influenced by Vloggers (70.20%). They have emerged as prominent opinion leaders as they create content about product evaluation and recommendations [6].

Table 2 Respondents' Purchase Decision based on Attractive Statements

No.	The celebrity endorser should/could	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Have a clear skin	3.36	Strongly Influential
2.	Be beautiful/handsome	2.82	Influential
3.	Have a fair skin tone	2.81	Influential
4.	Have a glowing skin	3.27	Strongly Influential
5.	Be physically fit	2.82	Influential
	Total Weighted Mean	3.01	Influential

In assessing attractiveness, the overall weighted mean was 3.01 implying it is collectively influential to the respondents. Physical attractiveness is important in making a positive impact on buying intentions perceived by the public [7].

Table 3 Respondents' Purchase Decision based on Expertise Statements

No.	The celebrity endorser should/could:	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Knowledgeable on the beauty products he/she is endorsing	3.89	Strongly Influential
2.	Able to identify what is the advantage and disadvantage of the product over other brands.	3.87	Strongly Influential
3.	Able to answer questions related to product	3.84	Strongly Influential
4.	Properly educated about the beauty product through seminars before endorsing it	3.78	Strongly Influential
5.	Have previously endorsed beauty product before	3.48	Strongly Influential
	Total Weighted Mean	3.77	Strongly Influential

For expertise, respondents believe that it is strongly influential in their decision-making with a 3.77 overall weighted mean. Celebrity endorsers' expertise is therefore valued by the respondents in buying beauty products [8].

Table 4 Respondents' Purchase Decision based on Trustworthiness Statements

NO.	The celebrity endorser must:	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Be trustworthy.	3.87	Strongly Influential
2.	Be honorable.	3.77	Strongly Influential
3.	Be likable.	3.67	Strongly Influential
4.	Be honest with pros and cons of the product.	3.89	Strongly Influential
5.	Have positive relationship with other people.	3.80	Strongly Influential
	Total Weighted Mean	3.80	Strongly Influential

Trustworthiness obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.88 interpreted as strongly influential to the respondents. It concurs with a study that a high level of trustworthiness has a significant influence on the buying intent of customers [9].

Table 5 Respondents' Purchase Decision based on Credibility Statements

NO.	The celebrity endorser must:	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Breliable on the information of the product that he/she is endorsing.	3.92	Strongly Influential
2.	Be confident in advertising the beauty product.	3.87	Strongly Influential
3.	Be consistent in using the beauty product they promote.	3.81	Strongly Influential
4.	Have an experience in using beauty products.	3.88	Strongly Influential
5.	Be unbiased in advertising the beauty product.	3.91	Strongly Influential
	Total Weighted Mean	3.88	Strongly Influential

Credibility garnered the highest overall weighted mean of 3.88, implying that respondents prefer endorser attributes over other traits of endorsers. A highly credible endorser has a favorable influence on a consumer's purchasing intentions [7].

Table 6 Respondents' Purchase Decision based on the Quality Attributes of Celebrity Endorsers

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I purchase beauty products endorsed by celebrities.	3.15	Influential
I purchase beauty products if my favorite celebrity is using it.	2.87	Influential
I can easily identify the beauty product because the celebrity is associated with it.	3.09	Influential
I trust the recommendation of the celebrity endorser.	2.94	Influential
I spend considerable time assessing the celebrity endorser in order to decide whether the beauty product is appropriate for me.	3.36	Strongly Influential
I pay a lot of attention to the celebrity endorser of the beauty product.	2.86	Influential
I rely on the celebrity endorser in evaluating the beauty product.	2.73	Influential
I used the claims of the celebrity endorser to evaluate the beauty products.	2.96	Influential

The variables of celebrity endorsers' quality attributes on purchase decision making of the respondents showed a total weighted mean of 3.06 interpreted as influential. Celebrity endorsement is a particularly effective communication technique since it has the capacity to attract attention [10].

Table 7 Spearman Rank Correlation between the Identified Qualities of Celebrities and Respondents' Purchase Decision Making

Variables Correlated	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Results
Attractiveness	0.263	Weak Positive	<0.001*	Reject Ho	Significant
Expertise	0.291	Weak Positive	<0.001*	Reject Ho	Significant
Trustworthiness	0.057	Negligible Positive	0.335	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Credibility	0.122	Negligible Positive	0.038*	Reject Ho	Significant

Asterisk (*) under column p-value indicates that the hypothesis is rejected as the correlation is significant at 0.05 level.

The Spearman Correlation Test revealed that attractiveness, expertise, and credibility of the endorsers have a significant relationship with purchase decision making with p values of 0.001, 0.001, and 0.038 respectively.

4. Conclusion

It could be concluded that attractiveness, credibility, and expertise show that there is a significant relationship to the respondents' purchase decision-making with a p-value of 0.001, 0.001, and 0.038 therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, for trustworthiness, the results indicated that there is no significant relation with the respondents' purchase decision making with a p-value of 0.035 implying that the null hypothesis for trustworthiness is accepted.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to extend their appreciation and gratitude to Cecilia D. Santiago, PhD Pharma, Dean and Mylene S. Andal, MSPharm, Professor and Centro Escolar University-Manila School of Pharmacy for providing consultation and research facilities.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The study protocol was approved on March 7, 2022, from Institutional Ethics Review Board (IERB) of Centro Escolar University and granted the reference number of CEU_IERB_2022-0368_SOP.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study

References

- [1] Affairs Oof R. Cosmetic overview for imported products [Internet]. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. FDA; [cited 2022]. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/industry/regulated-products/cosmetics-overview>

- [2] Diller, V. Can Beauty Actually Improve Your Health? [Internet]. New York: Huffpost; 2015 [Cited 2022] Available from: https://www.huffpost.com/entry/can-beauty-actually-impro_b_7954910.
- [3] Roberts, R. 2022 Beauty Industry Trends & Cosmetics Marketing: Statistics and Strategies for Your Ecommerce Growth. Miami: Common Thread; 2022 [Cited 2022]. Available from <https://commonthreadco.com/blogs/coachs-corner/beauty-industry-cosmetics-marketing-ecommerce>.
- [4] Nwulu CS, Udo MI. A theoretical reflection of celebrity endorsement in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Economic Development*. 2015, 3(2): 88-89.
- [5] Das P. (2017). Wearing makeup gives women confidence and makes them feel smarter. United States: Science Times; 2017 [Cited 2022]. Available from <https://www.sciencetimes.com/articles/17703/20170801/wearing-makeup-gives-women-confidence-and-makes-them-feel-smarter.htm>
- [6] Lee JE, Watkins B. YouTube vloggers' influence on consumer luxury brand perceptions and intentions. *Journal of Business Research*, Elsevier. 2016, 69(12): 5753-60.
- [7] Gong W, Li X. Engaging Fans on Microblog: The Synthetic Influence of Parasocial Interaction and Source Characteristics on Celebrity Endorsement. *Psychology & Marketing*. 2017, 34 (7): 720-732.
- [8] Eyob H. How does expert endorsement affect consumer's perceived credibility?. Sweden: Luleå University of Technology; 2018.
- [9] Singh RP, Banarjee N. Exploring the Influence of Celebrity Credibility on Brand Attitude, Advertisement Attitude and Purchase Intention. SAGE Publication. 2020, 19(6): 1622-1639.
- [10] Adam MA, Hussain N. Impact of celebrity endorsement on consumer buying behavior. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*. 2019, 5(3): 79-121.